

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Supplementary Figure S1. Representative images of patients' MRI and patients' surgically resected tumor specimens. Representative sagittal T1-weighted (upper panels) and axial T1-weighted MRI (lower panels) and resected tumor specimens of MFS and UPS. MFS MRI shows a highly intense mass signal typical of myxoid matrix in subcutaneous tissues (upper left panel) and tail-like margin (lower left panel) at caudal extent of lesion. UPS MRI shows an extensive palpable mass in the left thigh, well-defined by a pseudocapsule (upper right panel) and with an infiltrative pattern in the subcutaneous and muscular tissue (lower right panel). MRI, magnetic resonance imaging.

Supplementary Figure S2. Representative images of IHC biomarkers detected in analyzed case series. H&E images of matched tumor specimens are shown (10 $\times$ and 20 $\times$ magnification). Positivity for actin was widespread and 50% Ki67 positivity was detected.

Supplementary Figure S3. Principal Component Analysis of the 500 most variable genes. **(A)** All samples. Color: number of aligned reads, shape: disease type. **(B)** Samples with more than 4 millions aligned reads. Color: response to drug in cell line, shape: disease type. **(C)** Samples with more than 4 millions aligned reads. Color: sequencing date, shape: sex. No clear correlation with histotype or responsiveness condition was observed. Sex and number of reads were identified as confounding variables and used to correct batch effect in subsequent analyses. The two replicates of repeated samples (000001, 000002 and 000003) showed consistent clustering, ensuring robustness of different library preparations across time. No apparent batch effect for sequencing date.

Supplementary Figure S4. cBioPortal *in silico* analyses of most relevant DEGs between MFS and UPS. Box plots showing mRNA expression of selected DEGs in MFS and UPS patients according to the Adult Soft Tissue Sarcomas (TCGA, Cell 2017) database.

Supplementary Table S1. Metadata of RNA-Seq cohort. The variables “patient_responder” and “line_responder” indicate whether the patient or his/her derived cell line responded to the drug treatment. Patient responder PR, patient non-responder PNR, patient unknown PUK. Line responder LR, line non-responder LNR, line unknown LUK. Only samples with more than 4 millions aligned reads were selected for differential expression analyses. Compared to the total sequenced reads, this number is a more accurate indicator of how many reads are actually “usable”, because kallisto aligns directly to the reference transcriptome instead of the genome, thereby excluding intergenic, intronic and ribosomal sequences.

sample id	condition	sex	line responder	patient responder	run date	aligned reads	total reads
cdfaus000001	UPS	F	LUK	PUK	22/11/22	6067833	30300690
cd-faus-000001	UPS	F	LUK	PUK	16/09/22	11218642	53370137
cdfaus000002	MFS	F	LR	PNR	22/11/22	723548	21988967
cd-faus-000002	MFS	F	LR	PNR	16/09/22	478512	16263165
cdfaus000003	UPS	M	LNR	PUK	22/11/22	4610152	30451074
cd-faus-000003	UPS	M	LNR	PUK	16/09/22	4245353	31576509
cd-faus-000004	UPS	F	LNR	PUK	16/09/22	17871848	66001817
cd-faus-000005	MFS	M	LUK	PUK	16/09/22	8216831	43809008
cd-faus-000006	MFS	M	LUK	PUK	16/09/22	3424978	30302994
cd-faus-000007	MFS	M	LR	PUK	16/09/22	8838977	42516797
cd-faus-000008	UPS	M	LUK	PUK	16/09/22	3762542	25698103
cdfaus000009	MFS	M	LUK	PUK	25/10/22	12281228	58024801
cdfaus000010	MFS	F	LUK	PUK	25/10/22	14191809	60662711
cdfaus000012	MFS	F	LNR	PNR	25/10/22	6506277	38927640
cdfaus000013	UPS	M	LUK	PR	25/10/22	17101505	63138235
cdfaus000014	UPS	F	LR	PUK	25/10/22	15282729	67167968
cdfaus000015	MFS	F	LUK	PR	25/10/22	11338272	56075509
cdfaus000016	UPS	F	LUK	PUK	25/10/22	1444517	29721159
cdfaus000017	MFS	M	LUK	PUK	22/11/22	11671595	55073216
cdfaus000018	MFS	M	LUK	PUK	22/11/22	20070723	67975497
cdfaus000019	UPS	F	LNR	PNR	22/11/22	294604	7942317
cdfaus000020	UPS	F	LNR	PUK	25/10/22	7483622	38795486

Supplementary Table S2. List of 164 differentially expressed genes between MFS vs. UPS.

gene ID	log2 FC	P adj
AC004223.3	15.9618172473031	0.0002458712201191
AC004890.3	-16.3332703834225	0.000121327967903
AC008695.1	15.8414631610817	0.0002871059806161
AC009879.2	-15.3647856983688	0.0004220419923386
AC027345.1	-15.5753215138031	0.0003176958198863
AC068631.2	-2.26860746276416	0.0327434122709978
AC069113.1	5.16987377539593	0.001403252073609
AC087888.1	14.8208101541327	0.0009733782536148
AC090616.4	14.9929740593766	0.0007987924167024
AC091492.1	4.29796520224436	0.0147754292459433
AC093063.1	14.8208101023694	0.0009733782536148
AC104073.3	15.983416770062	0.0002407638443851
AC107027.2	14.9929740593766	0.0007987924167024
AC108479.2	-15.3647856732324	0.0004220419923386
AC108734.3	4.94072832662592	0.000699480013736
ACKR4	3.28284038849583	0.0015753439572696
ACTN3	5.76395644727847	0.0018763872406717
ADAMDEC1	-2.21340109290272	0.0445214047025642
ADAMTS5	2.26722706931994	0.0133186190826569
ADCY8	4.16816529121508	0.0309250234925666
ADM2	-1.63460191359183	0.0001587764984059
AKR1C3	2.20617863194936	0.0042712279622422
AL049650.1	-15.3155086284832	0.0004220419923386
AL357075.2	14.8208101023694	0.0009733782536148
AL391099.1	-16.3332708479445	0.000121327967903
AL445665.1	3.33442953233582	0.0004125533149946
AL513124.1	14.8208101023694	0.0009733782536148
AL589655.1	-15.5571329921752	0.0003231529811994
AL713999.1	-15.5753215154746	0.0003176958198863
ALDH1A2	4.09740865641005	0.0002727109116002
ALDH7A1P2	-15.3647856732324	0.0004220419923386
ANKDD1B	2.76637607626906	0.0023534720052293
AP002472.1	16.335864939693	0.0001398785056168
AQP7P1	4.06890178681342	0.0142905628758345
ARL17A	-1.01183943454347	0.036560758369144
ARPC3P1	-16.3332712204058	0.000121327967903
ASB5	4.97981174312597	0.0420367665034581
ASTN1	4.64818004595643	0.0003374040187902
ATAD3C	-0.820921187735636	0.0420805051339646
ATP2B2	3.85760200968866	0.041845627727631
BMP7	3.44955027074572	0.0035116340181039
BTC	4.23642836029443	0.0029019545057517
C8B	14.9929740593766	0.0007987924167024
CDH19	2.86105530260366	0.031096789580076
CHL1	2.92717207788185	0.021750755363307
CKM	11.4673104759142	0.0051906318466829
COL10A1	-3.09263928865137	0.0320928749724517
COL11A1	-2.66550222291716	0.0059685066312583
CPB1	2.56521893248728	0.0215443289924312
CR383656.5	-15.5571329921752	0.0003231529811994
CRMP1	2.40359396124438	0.0026558628421131
CYP26B1	2.02420577996164	0.0471894436664504
CYP2C18	5.68622419144212	0.0445214047025642
CYP4F12	3.33055844821841	0.0118875753381738
CYP4Z1	3.93212623051381	0.0417604956347374
DLX3	5.48735283057738	0.0002703988453264
DNAJC3	-0.706209292912778	0.0007286485164413
DNER	4.60222666040332	0.0393563081209593
DSG2	2.77842306906081	0.0171279520035367
EPB41L4B	4.82491114243625	0.0016004817851006
FABP3	3.14595223598309	0.044091928428558
FAM133B	-1.25995259588239	0.0195349126026633
FGB	14.8208101541327	0.0009733782536148

FGD6	-1.06215122059221	0.0325482532970597
FGF16	3.6564492349488	0.0003231529811994
FKBP1AP4	-15.364785702271	0.0004220419923386
FRAS1	2.92864205653294	0.0042164517722578
GALNT8	2.65413943855352	0.0410968940713804
GAPDHP57	14.9929730143577	0.0007987924167024
GAS2L2	4.19722498176634	0.041845627727631
GC	14.8208101023694	0.0009733782536148
GNB1	-0.863027168793794	0.0134574125570823
GPAA1P1	-15.5272865699881	0.0003234560616273
GPIHBP1	2.56671375834475	0.0407296258600645
GPR158	-2.91498465332925	0.0446224240829561
GREM1	-3.96707394790137	0.0252402530627861
GRIN2D	-2.24697711792315	0.0100898413131509
HHATL	4.61593792165837	0.0044587183577878
HLA-DQB1	-2.35249181189002	0.0276835615852978
HPGDS	2.06816654633192	0.047728717701912
HRASLS5	3.6554165786748	0.0151280047069652
HSD17B3	4.57702234233832	0.0001947232384084
HTR3C	14.820810392278	0.0009733782536148
IGFN1	-2.75102303691553	0.0393563081209593
IGHV3-43	8.16396063818042	0.0408890123621263
IL17D	3.07113162219454	0.0045520590880887
IL1B	-1.85661916721595	0.0155264855844394
IVL	5.73971221519492	0.0308146263146991
KHDRBS3	2.54208794200134	0.0405682537728084
KIF26B	-3.00876844447297	0.0318997176853113
KRT18	-2.8042109822999	0.0141534553647841
LGALS9DP	-15.3155086942688	0.0004220419923386
LHX5	-15.5753215154746	0.0003176958198863
LMO3	3.38086494714418	0.0044587183577878
LONRF2	2.58897597084162	0.0086222303874118
LRP1B	4.74693337917509	0.0011339843136861
LRRC17	2.37430362799528	0.0010766827756662
LYZ	-1.98982699985808	0.0451039055080043
METTL27	2.28309473111045	0.0391392125804533
MMP13	-3.18603742123275	0.0234925834812785
MMP28	3.47715359872779	0.0015230943501245
MRPL50P4	14.8208101541327	0.0009733782536148
MRPS17P5	16.3358646637489	0.0001398785056168
MYOCD	4.30815274925042	0.0016440059960956
MYOM2	4.59220957396077	0.043833880792418
MYRIP	2.91670652116563	0.039840032908707
NAALAD2	2.35705846103528	0.0005101713948174
NHLH1	3.11143670601819	0.0392543919764671
NPIPA2	-4.70152227198323	0.0001155566647023
NTRK2	2.52786666050622	0.0059575388085954
NXN	-2.02037768611734	0.0154601446234107
PCDH20	4.45753188750469	0.0264674198380483
PCNPP3	16.4876172169571	0.0001208645244036
PCOLCE2	2.1631851769221	0.0446224240829561
PDK4	2.96928730759745	0.0005306336713143
PI3	5.55115511664382	0.0208548318332566
PLAC9	2.28418509057714	0.0106300936135112
PLAC9P1	5.68767383220734	0.0037878214844857
PLIN1	2.35610389648226	0.0002764591027898
PPARGC1A	3.72909389657901	0.0007580997397157
PPT1	-0.824792808514447	0.0461506721477938
PRIMA1	4.29551709320911	0.0319675953544754
PXDNL	3.00733461005014	0.0160030160227815
RGS10	-1.0907463743096	0.0215443289924312
RNF138P1	2.03253911382404	0.0267171633796467
RNF32	4.46114667399949	0.0134440761906231
SCARA5	2.72320212859352	0.0308146263146991
SELL	-2.50082854750355	0.0130239822522334
SEMA6D	2.22477956213816	0.0153505139148723
SEPT14P24	-16.3332703834225	0.000121327967903

SGCG	4.65523822030465	0.0345967991826796
SH3GL2	5.00040012252031	0.0007716189808496
SHISA6	6.15484652260079	0.0038553205424621
SLC26A7	3.54029329268047	0.0018410644591154
SLC35G3	5.35067767767691	0.0391392125804533
SLC7A7	-1.03978158561578	0.0478168892802352
SLPI	4.82205996769061	0.0020321211750025
SMIM34A	-15.3564930451627	0.0004220419923386
SP5	4.4279249707088	0.015917194907142
SPTA1	3.64150582948484	0.004792417580334
SRSF1P1	-15.0095555916919	0.0006344101244477
SUGCT	-3.125430564153	0.0002683149616496
SYN2	2.78852480934909	0.0104010221570647
TCEA1P3	-15.5571329921752	0.0003231529811994
TCHH	4.08440993918848	0.0012955490559348
TENM1	3.04452761820424	0.0019394303821618
THRSP	4.34331267081919	0.0274294209466968
TLX3	-15.5753215154746	0.0003176958198863
TMEM100	2.6557432540096	0.0144105955215373
TMEM183B	-15.3647856983688	0.0004220419923386
TMEM235	-15.3647856732324	0.0004220419923386
TRARG1	3.71964757752509	0.0043972183377072
TRAV39	14.9929705733892	0.0007987924167024
TRBV5-5	14.8396557625386	0.0009733782536148
TREML5P	-15.3647856854246	0.0004220419923386
UQCRBP2	-15.5753215154746	0.0003176958198863
USP8P1	-15.3630677935258	0.0004220419923386
VASN	2.95974469747897	0.0393362042444603
VEGFD	3.77901457640021	0.0407296258600645
VIT	3.54505078597619	0.0155839116786768
VMO1	-2.59492225561523	0.016530240825166
WNT7B	-4.43934582423426	0.0273713151474691
ZBTB7C	2.61396880069467	0.0466347127333659
ZNF281	-1.41135812503621	0.0007286485164413

Supplementary Table S3. List of 61 differentially expressed genes between LR vs. LNR.

hugo	log2FoldChange	padj
AC009299.2	-21.078538076485	0.0007717068274952
AC022149.1	-20.040608676543	0.0003961209563829
AC058822.1	-20.3087603324419	0.0001645198352295
AC211476.4	-19.8979480456708	0.0006197894062902
AP002748.4	6.2866899638767	0.0394520080999162
ARFGEF3	2.36037224254514	0.0394821439708152
CELSR1	3.6443484561473	0.0006511618890153
CLCA2	8.25959292659431	0.0170194834282316
COL24A1	3.09993138656069	0.0367409476044726
COL25A1	4.67749700432024	0.0396646056613214
CSMD2	3.36106747376481	0.0335790991629667
DACT2	5.09310115862784	0.0334584780645987
DCHS1	2.13372616219	0.0205683629467067
DES	7.26068305501764	0.0001108809700243
DNAJB9	-2.64723219540979	0.0241158114031642
EPB41L4B	6.91055232509177	0.0350490454477043
EPHA2	3.9856944632967	0.0007097585398383
EXPH5	2.89843998067434	0.01753964061397
F8A2	-21.6529446755791	0.0004829220438438
FAM160A1	3.48839152843989	0.0078426376743799
FLG2	7.0418864528687	0.000643701097793
HR	6.53109134781659	0.0002427483147194
IGHV1-69-2	-20.1899444786886	0.0002347888444572
IGHV3-71	-19.7084959558162	0.0012133604653388
IGHV3-72	-21.5098910669662	0.0005389195894617
IGHV4-80	-22.8195548609884	0.000177034991539
IGKV1D-13	-22.5823509011549	0.0002176209727504
IGKV2D-30	-20.3260735571351	0.0003852231336448
IGKV3D-15	-22.6416627640903	0.0002111967351457
IGLV3-10	-22.5450319412398	0.0002187131005134
KCNA1	3.81955300983825	0.0461380960409343
KLF5	3.62035387324976	0.0028652890106504
KRT10	5.217400076966	0.0266323645241322
KRT15	4.07308348971676	0.016597484908393
KRT80	4.53306605310334	0.0092058327276174
LRRC1	2.65594086960105	0.0061951188891722
MAL2	6.9584524603153	0.0037515467380701
MB	6.80326509110681	0.0098806936418512
MDFI	5.2621491491399	0.018749529899488
MTCO3P12	5.37733135474286	0.0266323645241322
NCAM1	4.47510481905812	0.0392798805117326
PER2	2.11093485566027	0.0037515467380701
PI16	5.04354851151404	0.0243958704215119
PLA2G4F	6.0002115470668	0.0243958704215119
PLIN4	3.7757896193885	0.0004341250300167
PRTG	3.80591791826704	0.0004829220438438
RPL21P16	-17.9564388419364	0.0012133604653388
SCG2	-6.44674471567122	0.0051459656164809
SELP	3.27692201328002	0.0411796207139576
SYT8	6.0021587368934	0.0266323645241322
TACR1	6.31792853736161	0.0093940906124578
TAP2	-7.44799792925909	0.0008401533554648
TERT	-21.6221847137359	0.0004870195353862
THBS4	4.18481952941251	0.0285661504047317
TLL1	3.92067958860773	0.0334584780645987
TMEM108	3.60370180838721	0.019746926004563
TNNI1	5.52451571786589	0.0138158950352574
TRIM29	6.01159381624771	0.0243958704215119
TRPV2	-2.5470566237312	0.0133306126591852
TSPAN11	4.06639214890321	0.042767046053139
USH2A	-6.2688404430615	0.0003852231336448